

DYNAMIC PERFORMANCE OF HB-CESIC[®] UNDER SEVERE CONDITIONS AND ITS APPLICATIONS

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1 Introduction

HB-Cesic[®] is a ceramic matrix composite that is manufactured by ECM. It is characterized by high stiffness and mechanical strength, high thermal conductivity, low CTE, and quick, relatively inexpensive manufacturing times. These characteristics make HB-Cesic[®] an ideal material at reasonable cost for large high-precision space optical and structural applications.

The starting material in the manufacturing of HB-Cesic[®] is a short, chopped, randomly oriented carbon fiber material, consisting of both pitch-based and other fibers. The fibers are mixed with a phenolic resin and molded into a blank, which then is heat-treated under vacuum. The result is a light-weight, porous, relatively brittle C/C greenbody. At the present time circular blanks are available in sizes up to 1.6 m, with a thickness up to 200 mm. By approximately the end of 2009, greenbody blocks up to 2 m in size or even larger will become available as circular or square blocks.

ECM's large CNC controlled milling machine of 2.5 x 1.75 m allows us to manufacture large, light-weighted, monolithic structures, such as mirrors and components for optical benches. For example, in the manufacture of optical mirrors, curved face sheets (including off-axis designs) can be machined with reinforcing ribs as thin as 1 mm and of any geometry, including ribs with light-weighting holes or of T-shape for increased stiffness.

Upon machining, the greenbody is infiltrated under vacuum conditions with liquid silicon at temperatures above 1600 °C. Capillary forces wick the silicon throughout the porous greenbody, where it reacts with the carbon matrix and the surfaces of the carbon fibers to form carbon fiber reinforced SiC -- HB-Cesic[®]. The density of the infiltrated HB-Cesic[®] composite is around 2.97 g/cm³.

After controlled cool-down, the HB-Cesic[®] structure is carefully examined visually and by other NDT methods, such as dye penetrant or ultrasonic tests. The structure is then micro-machined with suitable diamond tools or by EDM machining to achieve the required surface figure and interface geometry (e.g., mirror adaptation and mounting). EDM machining is possible because of HB-Cesic[®]'s good electrical conductivity. This machining method is fast compared to grinding, it is relatively inexpensive, and it yields a surface and location accuracy (e. g., for screw holes and mounts) of about 10 μm tolerance over a large area.

Manufacturing times of HB-Cesic[®] mirrors and other structures are typically only a few weeks, upon procurement of the C/C raw material, which is much shorter than the manufacturing times of other ceramic or glass structures. Highly complex and large projects take somewhat longer, e.g., mirrors with closed backs, meter-plus-class mirrors that require precision joining of greenbody or infiltrated segments, and large multi-segmented optical benches.

The maximum size of HB-Cesic® components is only limited by the size of the Si-infiltration furnaces. ECM's current largest furnace has a useable diameter of 2.4 m with up to three levels, each of height 1.2 m.

In Table 1, we summarize the currently established mechanical and thermal properties of HB-Cesic® under static conditions [1][2].

Table 1 HB-Cesic® material properties, static conditions.

Property	Unit	Value
Density	g/cm ³	2.97
Bending strength	MPa	320
Young's modulus	GPa	350
Poisson's ratio	--	0.18
CTE @ RT	ppm/K	2.3
Thermal conductivity @ RT	W/(m K)	125

2 Material characterization of HB-Cesic® under dynamic conditions

In addition to having data on the static performance of composite materials, it is also necessary to determine their performance under dynamic loads. This is particularly important when designing and machining components that approach the limits of the material's stability, in order to calculate sufficient safety factors. Therefore, ECM and its Japanese partner, Composites R&D, tested HB-Cesic® samples under dynamic loads, including:

- 4-pt bending strength
- Fracture toughness
- Fatigue test
- Shock test

2.1 Four-Point Bending Strength

2.1.1 Test Setup and Standard

For the 4-point bending test we used the test method of the Japanese Industrial Standard JIS R1601 for measuring flexural properties of continuous fiber-reinforced ceramic composites. Several measurement campaigns performed by different labs in Europe and Japan have demonstrated that this method can also be applied to measuring the flexural properties of short, chopped fiber-reinforced ceramics, such as ECM's HB-Cesic® material.

According to the Japanese Industrial Standard JIS R1601, the thickness and width of the test bars have to be determined within 0.02 mm. For our tests, we silicon-infiltrated test bars that closely matched the JIS standard size requirements. We machined the loaded span areas to the required 0.02 mm flatness.

A Shimadzu universal test machine was used to measure the mechanical performance of the HB-Cesic® test samples. Their size was 40.0 mm (l) x 4.0 mm (w) x 3.0mm (t), and the upper and lower support spans were 10.0 mm and 30.0 mm, respectively.

Fig.1 Test setup with HB-Cesic® sample.

We carried out the test using load rates of 0.1 mm/min, 10 mm/min and 1000 mm/min. The load speed of 0.1 mm/min is equivalent to static load tests. Five samples were tested for each load rate.

In addition to these dynamic tests, we also tested the effect of the surface preparation of the samples by preparing samples of the same size, but with different surface finishes. The different surface preparations were done by:

- Sandblasting
- Wire EDM machining
- Grinding D126
- Grinding D400
- Grinding D600

For each different surface finish we prepared 10 samples.

2.1.2 Results

The results of the 4-point bending tests under different load conditions were listed in Table 2.

Table 2 HB-Cesic® material properties under dynamic conditions.

Load Rate	mm/min	0.1	10	1000
Strength	MPa	323.47	334.46	332.2
Standard Deviation	MPa	18.94	11.75	5.27
Coefficient of Variation	%	5.86	3.51	1.59

These positive results of the 4-point bending tests demonstrate that HB-Cesic® is suitable for the construction of structures and mirrors that must withstand extreme dynamic loads. Furthermore, the tests demonstrate that at a load rate of 0.1 mm/min. HB-Cesic® performs identically as under static loads.

In addition, our 4-point bending tests with samples of different surface preparations show that surface preparation has a significant effect on the performance of HB-Cesic®. For instance,

even between different grades of grinding, the tests show an improvement in the samples' strength of about 30 % from D126 to D600.

In Fig.2, we show the correlation between the samples' surface preparation and 4-point bending strength.

Fig.2. Four point bending strength vs. surface preparation

2.2 Fracture Toughness – K_{IC}

2.2.1 Test Setup and Standard

In order to get realistic results, we measured fracture toughness with 20 HB-Cesic® samples. The test was carried out under 3-point bending load conditions according to the Japanese Industrial Standard JIS R1607.

- a = crack length 0.5 mm
- B = width of the sample 4.0 mm
- W = thickness of sample 3.0 mm
- S = distance of span support 12.0 mm

Fig.3 K_{IC} sample definition

2.2.2 Results

The results of these tests based on 20 samples, are given in Table 3.

Table 3 Results of fracture toughness measurements

K _{1c}	MPa m ^{1/2}	3.72
Standard Deviation	MPa m ^{1/2}	0.18
Coefficient of Variation	%	4.92

As the table shows, the fracture toughness of HB-Cesic® is 3.72 MPa m^{1/2}. This relatively large value of K_{1c} is important in the design of ultra-lightweight, large-scale structures and reflectors because it indicates good damage tolerance to cracks. Together with a very good damping coefficient of 1.5 to 2%, HB-Cesic® offers minimal risks to damages under dynamic loads.

In actual applications, it is impossible to fabricate an entirely defect-free structure. Any defects can lead to fracturing during handling and mechanical testing, such as vibrations and acoustic impacts, or during launch. Materials having high damage tolerance enable designs of thinner, lighter structures and reflectors-

2.3 Fatigue test

2.3.1 Test Setup and Standard

For the fatigue test we manufactured 30 bending samples with the same size as for the 4-pt bending tests, i.e., with 40.0 x 4.0 x 3.0 mm. In order to ensure that all 30 samples will perform adequately, we performed a screening test in which each sample was loaded to 288 MPa (90% of the static average 4-point bending strength of 320 MPa).

We then selected randomly 10 samples from the 30 samples, which we tested under cycling

loads at 25 Hz between 10% to 80% of the average static 4-point bending strength of 320 MPa. Thus, 10 samples were cycled between 32 MPa and 256 MPa. Each sample was tested through 500,000 cycles.

2.3.2 Results

The fatigue testing yielded some rather good results. In the screening test, only 3 of the 30 samples broke below 288 MPa; and none broke below 265 MPa.

During the fatigue test, 9 samples survived the 500,000 cycles. Only 1 sample broke earlier, namely, after 102,000 cycles.

In the final rupture test, the 9 samples that survived the 500,000 cycles broke at an average load of 318 MPa ±20 MPa.

2.4 Dynamic shock test

2.4.1 Test Setup and Standard

In an internal R&D test campaign we performed dynamic shock tests on a representative mirror substrate with extremely thin wall thicknesses of just 1.2 – 1.5 mm. In order to determine the performance of such an extremely thin structure, we performed the shock tests at a Japanese test facility which is specialized in dynamic testing of large structures. During this test, the sample was exposed to shock levels of 100g in X/Y and Z directions ("g" refers to the Earth's gravitational acceleration). Nine tests were carried out in which the mounting of the mirror substrate was changed from 3 to 12 contact points and shock loads of up to 100 g were applied. The objective of these tests was to determine if the mirror substrate would survive these dynamic shock loads as finite element model calculations predicted it would. To avoid direct contact between the metallic table and the HB-Cesic® structure PTFE spacers were used between them. The dynamic shock test was done according to the following test matrix.

Table 4 Test matrix

Mounting Points	Max. Load: 100 g
12	30%
12	60%
12	100 %
6	30%
6	60%
6	100 %
3	30%
3	60%
3	100 %

2.4.2 Results

The mirror substrate survived all 9 dynamic shock tests despite the very thin wall thicknesses.

After each of the 9 tests, we cycled the substrate through a sine test, using the same contact points and loads, in order to determine if there might be failure due to micro-cracks or other defects. No failures occurred during any of the 9 follow-on sine tests.

These results constitute a realistic demonstration of the mechanical strength and reliability of our HB-Cesic® material even under such severe conditions.

3 Conclusions

These tests described in this paper demonstrate that HB-Cesic® composite material has the same performance under dynamic loads as under static loads and HB-Cesic® performs reliably even under severe conditions. This is consistent with several measurement campaigns we carried out already in the past.

Especially the insensitivity of HB-Cesic® to fatigue is very promising for future applications, such as the design and construction of large

structures and mirrors that must withstand high and cycled loads.

In the future we plan to carry out further tests of HB-Cesic® focussing on additional material properties and under dynamic loads.

References

[1] M. Kroedel, T. Ozaki, M. Kume, A. Furuya, Y. Yui, H. Imai, H. Katayama, Y. Tange, T. Nakagawa and H. Kaneda, “Manufacturing and performance test of a 800 mm space optic”. *Proceedings of SPIE*, San Diego, U.S.A, 7018, 2008.

[2] M. Kroedel and T. Ozaki, “Development of HB- Cesic® Composite for Space Optics and Structures”. *Proceedings of 26th International Symposium on Space technology and Science*, Hamamatsu, Japan, 2008.